

Rapid microgeographic evolution in response to climate change

Authors

A. Z. Andis Arietta, Yale University, School of the Environment (corresponding author)

David K. Skelly, Yale University, School of the Environment

Correspondence: a.andis@yale.edu; 370 Prospect St., New Haven, CT 06511

Supporting Material

1. Canopy cover

Methods

Canopy changes over time through successional changes in species composition, maturation, or short-term changes due to disturbance like beaver alterations, fire, wind-fall, or timber harvest. Above-canopy radiation is affected by the time of day, sky clarity, and season (Promis, 2013). The understory light environment is a function of the interaction between the light blocked by the canopy and the magnitude and angle of solar radiation above the canopy.

Hemispherical photos can be used to characterize canopy closure at a given point in the understory (Jennings et al., 1999) and can be used in conjunction with solar radiation models to integrate total or average radiation incident at that point over any time interval (Rich, 1989; Promis et al., 2012). Individual points estimates can be treated as spatial samples and averaged to estimate light environment over space.

We estimated contemporary light environment for Wood frog breeding ponds as the proportion of direct and indirect radiation incident upon a point below the canopy to the same point absent the canopy (Anderson, 1964) using hemispherical photos captured in 2017 and 2018.

For each pond, we took photos at each of the cardinal points (N, S, E, W) 1m in from the bank along the spring high-water perimeter and in the center (C) of the pond at the intersection of the N-S and E-W lines. We captured one set of 5 photos during the summer while the canopy was in full leaf and 5 photos at the same points during the winter after the leaves had fallen. All photos were taken approximately 1.5 vertical meters above the spring high water height with a handheld leveling system.

Hemispherical photos require processing into binarized images prior to analysis (Rich, 1990; Glatthorn and Beckschäfer, 2014). Many errors can arise when camera settings, corrective editing, or binarization techniques are inappropriate. In the field, we captured photos on uniformly overcast days. We standardized exposure settings to the sky by setting ISO, aperture, and shutter speed so that the open sky was at exposure value 0, then down-stepped shutter speed by two stops. This ensures that the grey value in the photos is standardized to the sky (Wagner, 1998). Even on uniformly overcast days, the sky brightness changes over time. To account for this, we captured

photos in RAW format and adjusted exposure values in Adobe Lightroom 5.7.1 to ensure that the brightest pixel grey value aligned to full white (Beckschäfer et al., 2013).

We exported images as full sized JPEG files from Lightroom and used Hemispherical_2.0 (Beckschäfer, 2015) plugin for ImageJ. Hemispherical_2.0 uses a “minimum” thresholding algorithm on the blue color plane of the image to classify each pixel as black or white. Binarized images were then converted to BMP format and analyzed in Gap Light Analyzer (Frazer et al., 1999). We parameterized the GLA models with estimates from the 1991-2010 Update to the National Solar Radiation Database (2010) for Hartford, Connecticut (approximately 40 km from the study site) [Citation: National Solar Radiation Database (2010) https://rredc.nrel.gov/solar/old_data/nsrdb/1991-2010/].

The typical pre-metamorphic period for wood frogs at our site begins with oviposition in early April and ends with metamorphosis by the end of August. Leaves typically emerge in Mid-may. Therefore, we estimated leaf-on and leaf-off GSF estimates from the set of summer photos over the period April 1 to May 15 and winter photos over the period May 16 to August 30, respectively. We calculated a spring + summer GSF for the period April 1 through August 30 as the weighted average of the leaf-on and leaf-off estimates with respect to the proportion of days before and after leaf emergence. Analyses for both seasonal windows and subsequent models incorporating spring + summer canopy are included in this appendix, but were not sufficiently different from the spring estimates to include in the manuscript.

These methods closely replicate those used by Halverson (Halverson et al., 2003) for the canopy closure estimates used by Skelly in the 2001 embryonic development rate experiment (Skelly, 2004), with two exceptions that may bias comparisons across time. First, the historical estimates were calculated with proprietary HemiView software rather than Gap Light Analyzer. These programs are analogous and we set identical parameters to mitigate bias. Second, the sampling layout for canopy photos differed between timespoints. Canopy values used in Skelly (2004) were estimated from hemispherical photos taken along the intersections of 5 m cartesian grids (2 to 172 photos per pond) and analyzed in HemiView software (Halverson et al., 2003) while contemporary photos were sampled at cardinal points and the center of the pond.

In order to compare these historical data to current estimates, we subsampled 5 points from the cartesian grid estimates, corresponding to the 4 cardinal point and 1 central point and tested for a difference in GSF estimates. We compared the pairwise differences between spring GSF estimated from the two methods using a paired t-test and estimated pearson’s correlation between estimates.

Results

Our dataset includes historical canopy estimates for 14 of the 16 ponds included in either the 2001 or 2018 experiment (excludes DT and E1). On average, leaf-off estimates of canopy closure from photos at the cardinal points and center of the ponds are 1.8% darker than estimates using photos taken along a cartesian grid, but the difference is not significant ($p = 0.08$, 95% C.I. = -3.9 - 0.3%). The estimates of leaf-off GSF from subsampled photos are tightly correlated with the original estimates ($R^2 = 0.92$) (Fig S1, A).

Larval period canopy closure is estimated to be significantly darker by 2.2% when comparing photos from cardinal points to those captured along a cartesian grid ($p = 0.04$, 95% C.I. = -4.3 - 0.1%) with similarly strong correlation between methods ($R^2 = 0.97$) (Fig S1, B).

Figure S1. Comparison of spring (A, leaf-off) and spring + summer (B, weighted mean leaf-on and leaf-off over wood frog aquatic development period) canopy closure estimates (GSF = Global Site Factor) for fourteen wood frog breeding ponds averaged over 2 to 172 photos captured at the intersection of 5m cartesian grids (Cartesian Grid) or a subsample of 5 photos captured at the 4 cardinal points and center (Cardinal Points) of each pond during 1999 and 2000 seasons. Colors indicate ponds that are represented in both experimental timepoints (black), only the 2001 experiment (red), and only the 2018 experiment (grey).

2. Pond temperature

Methods

Over the past few decades, air temperatures in our region have been increasing, but the magnitude varies across the season. Summer temperatures during the wood frog larval period have increased more than two-fold compared to temperatures during the embryonic period (Arietta et al., 2020). Temperature-mediated selection during either period may drive evolutionary changes in embryonic development. Therefore, we estimated long-term average temperatures for two seasonal windows from day-of-year 91 to 135 and day-of-year 91 to 168. These windows correspond to the leaf-off period of embryonic and early larval development and the aquatic development period, respectively.

Starting in 2001, we recorded water temperatures in a subset of the 60 wood frog breeding ponds at our field site. We recorded water temperature in breeding ponds every 0.5 or 1 hour with submersible temperature loggers (HOB0 8K Pendant (Onset Computer Corporation)) suspended 10cm below the surface at the deepest point in the pond. Loggers were deployed within days of oviposition (approximately DOY 91) and removed after larvae had metamorphosed or the pond dried (approximately DOY 168) (Fig S2). We computed daily means from the hourly data and restricted our

data to the window of greatest data saturation (DOY 91 to 168), resulting in 18,524 daily observations from 34 ponds over 18 years between 2001 and 2019 for our training dataset.

We imputed missing temperature values with a random forest model implemented in **randomForest** (v4.6.14 (Liaw and Wiener, 2002)) trained on all ponds at our site. Regression trees included both climate and site predictor variables. Climate variables included daily maximum, minimum and average temperature, radiation, precipitation, snowpack, and atmospheric pressure from the Daymet database (v.3 (Thornton et al., 2016)). We included a 1-day lag for all climate variables. Site variables included elevation, aspect, latitude, and a factor for individual ponds. A random noise variable was included in the set of predictor variables to assess relative importance. We grew our random forest from 300 regression trees (Fig S3) and used 10-fold cross validation to evaluate the predictive accuracy for imputed points.

Results

We grew our random forest from 300 trees with 8 predictor variables randomly tried at each split. Forest explained 87.5% of the variance in the data (RMSR = 1.32). Air temperature was the most important variable in both accuracy (i.e. reducing out-of-bag error) and node purity (i.e. correctly splitting trees) (Fig S4). On average, our predicted daily pond temperatures are off by +/- 0.54 C as assessed by 10-fold cross validation. In total, we imputed 29,212 observations, 61% of the total dataset.

Figure S2. The number of daily observations across all 34 ponds and 18 years (2001 to 2019) included in the random forest training dataset. Loggers were deployed coincident with oviposition (+/- 2-3 days) and removed after larvae metamorphosed and left the pond or the pond dried.

Figure S3. Decrease in error, estimated by out-of-bag cross-validation, for increasing numbers of trees included in the random forest model predicting daily pond water temperature.

Figure S4. Importance of variable in predictive accuracy of the random forest model prediction

daily pond water temperatures measured by the percentage decrease in mean square error of the out-of-bag cross-validation estimates when each variable is included (A) and the total decrease in node impurity (i.e. number of correctly estimated leaves) by splitting on each variable (B). Both importance estimates were averages across all trees. Variables included average, minimum, and maximum daily pond water temperature (TempC, minTempC, maxTempC), daily atmospheric pressure (Press), daily solar radiation incident upon Earth's service (Rad), daily precipitation (Precip), and daily snow water equivalent (SWE). For all daily climate variables, a 1-day lag was also included (L1). Canopy variables included Global Site Factor values for the leaf-on (GSFon), leaf-off (GSFoff), and weighted average over the growing season (wtGSF) and the standard deviations in these measures across the five estimates for each pond (sd). Variable for Pond identity, elevation, aspect, and latitude (Lat) were included. A random noise variable (noise) was included to assess relative importance.

3. Environmental change

Results

Pond	Δ Leaf-off GSF	Δ Weighted GSF	Δ Spring water temperature	Δ Aquatic period water temperature	Experiment
BO	-13.6	-5.36	0.26	0.34	2001, 2018
BS	-2.57	-1.96	0.02	0.38	2001, 2018
CC	-12.05	-5.86	-0.33	-0.11	2001
CP	-5.38	-16.66	-0.13	0.14	2001, 2018
DE	-7.1	-2.09	-0.33	-0.09	2001, 2018
GB	-8.1	-4.88	-0.15	0.03	2001, 2018
KE	0.59	-3.26	0.06	0.31	2001, 2018
LA	0.02	-8.48	0.14	0.18	2018
LT	-36.19	-26	-0.04	0.22	2001
MB	-13.56	-14.98	0.37	1.27	2001
MI	-14.77	-8.57	0.02	0.16	2001, 2018
SH	0.41	-8.21	0.11	0.31	2001, 2018
WF	-3.65	0.19	0.03	0.19	2001, 2018
WP	-12.49	-6.64	-0.2	-0.02	2018
Mean	-9.17	-8.05	-0.01	0.24	NA

Figure S5. Change in pond temperature in relation to canopy for 14 wood frogs ponds between 2001 and 2018 for spring (A) and spring and summer (B) seasonal windows. Red points indicate populations that ceased to host breeding populations between 2001 and 2018. Circles represent ponds represented in both 2001 and 2018 datasets. Spring pond temperatures are averaged over the period of DOY 91 to 135 and spring canopy is the average leaf-off canopy closure values for the same period. This corresponds to the embryonic development period of wood frogs. Spring and summer temperatures are averaged over the period DOY 91 to 168. Spring and summer canopy values are the weighted average of leaf-off and leaf-on canopy closure values from DOY 91 to 243. Marginal boxplots show the mean and interquartile range of pond-wise values.

Figure S6. Change in pond temperature in relation to canopy for 16 wood frogs ponds between

2001 (point) and 2018 (label) for spring (A) and spring and summer (B) seasonal windows. Red labels indicate populations that ceased to host breeding populations between 2001 and 2018. Grey labels indicate ponds for which conditions in 2001 are unknown. Spring pond temperatures are averaged over the period of DOY 91 to 135 and spring canopy is the average leaf-off canopy closure values for the same period. This corresponds to the embryonic development period of wood frogs. Spring and summer temperatures are averaged over the period DOY 91 to 168. Spring and summer canopy values are the weighted average of leaf-off and leaf-on canopy closure values from DOY 91 to 243.

4. Embryonic development and size

Results

Figure S7. Embryonic development rates of wood frog embryos collected within 24 hours of oviposition in 2001 (A) and 2018 (B) and reared in incubators representing high (red) or low (blue) temperatures experienced across natal ponds until hatching (approximately Gosner state 20). Curves represent marginal fits of mixed effect models. Embryos were photographed throughout development in order to estimate developmental stage.

Figure S8. Embryonic period duration for each embryo was estimated from developmental growth rates corrected for differences in realized incubator temperatures. This was accomplished by including incubator temperature as a continuous variable in the growth rate models. The effect of incubator temperature was then held constant at the midpoint between years (a difference of +/- 0.2 C for the low temperature treatment or +/-0.15 C for the high temperature treatment) when predicting embryonic periods. Uncorrected estimates are shown (transparent) behind the corrected estimates (solid). Lines connect treatment groups from the same year.

Table S2. Mixed effect model results testing for difference in initial embryo volume between 2001 and 2018 experiment with random intercepts for clutchmates nested within pond. Year 2001 is the baseline value for the categorical Year variable. $N_{year} = 2$, $N_{pond} = 24$, $N_{clutch} = 134$, $N_{obs} = 1526$.

	Vol.mm3		
<i>Predictors</i>	<i>Estimates</i>	<i>CI</i>	<i>p</i>
(Intercept)	4.18	3.85 - 4.53	<0.001
Year [2018]	1.15	0.67 - 1.63	<0.001
Random Effects			
σ^2	0.16		
b_1 Year:Pond:Clutch	0.44		
b_0 Year:Pond	0.24		

Marginal R ² / Conditional R ²	0.28 / 0.86		
---	-------------	--	--

Table S3. Mixed effect model results testing for difference in initial embryonic period between 2001 and 2018 experiment with random intercepts for ponds. Year 2001 is the baseline value for the categorical Year variable. N_{pond} = 15, N_{obs(Low)} = 735, N_{obs(High)} = 744.

	EP (Low temperature treatment)			EP (High temperature treatment)		
<i>Predictors</i>	<i>Estimates</i>	<i>CI</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>Estimates</i>	<i>CI</i>	<i>p</i>
(Intercept)	12.46	11.99 - 12.95	<0.001	9.07	8.82 - 9.32	<0.001
Year [2018]	-1.77	-2.43 - -1.09	<0.001	-1.60	-1.93 - -1.28	<0.001
Random Effects				Random Effects		
σ ²	0.69			0.12		
b _{Year:Pond}	0.64			0.17		
Marginal R ² / Conditional R ²	0.37 / 0.67			0.69 / 0.87		

5. Countergradient variation

Results

Model selection tables

Table S4. Model selection table predicting embryonic period by leaf-off canopy (Can) and spring water temperatures (Temp) for the 2001 and 2018 experimental cohorts and vary with temperature treatment (Treat). Pond-wise random intercepts were included in all models. The difference in AIC compared to the best model in each year is represented as Δ AIC.

		2018		2001	
Model	Parameters	AIC	Δ AIC	AIC	Δ AIC
Treat * Can	6	1355.1	80.6	1689.3	0
Treat * Temp	6	1335.2	60.7	1702.7	13.4

Treat * Can + Treat * Temp	8	1314.1	39.6	1692.8	3.5
Treat * Can * Temp	10	1274.5	0	1689.8	0.5

Larval season countergradient regressions

Figure S9. Partial effect plots for embryonic period duration estimated with linear mixed effect models for 2018 (top row, A & B) and 2001 (bottom row, C & D) cohorts when reared in a common garden at high (red) and low (blue) temperature treatments. The effect of larval period pond temperature gradient while holding canopy at the mean (A & C) and the effect of spring and summer canopy gradient while holding temperature at the mean (B & D) are shown. Points represent pond-wise average fit (i.e. model fit plus conditional residuals). 95% confidence intervals for the regression line were estimated by fitting the models to 1000 non-parametric bootstrap replicates.

Table S5. Mixed effect regression results for estimating the effect of larval period pond temperatures (PondTemp) and spring and summer canopy cover (Canopy) on embryonic period for the 2018 and 2001 experimental cohorts.

Predictors	EP (2018)			EP (2001)		
	Estimates	CI	p	Estimates	CI	p
Intercept	5.78	1.92 – 9.50	<0.01	6.71	-6.93 – 19.34	0.32
Treatment _{Low}	-1.51	-3.24 – 0.09	0.07	3.78	0.18 – 7.76	0.04
PondTemp	0.13	-0.17 – 0.43	0.40	0.15	-0.81 – 1.25	0.77

Canopy	0.00	-0.12 – 0.12	0.99	0.04	-0.28 – 0.37	0.77
Treatment _{Low} * PondTemp	0.42	0.30 – 0.55	<<0.01	-0.07	-0.38 – 0.21	0.65
Treatment _{Low} * Canopy	0.07	0.03 – 0.13	<0.01	-0.01	-0.10 – 0.07	0.82
PondTemp * Canopy	0.00	-0.01 – 0.01	0.96	0.00	-0.03 – 0.02	0.82
Treatment _{Low} * PondTemp * Canopy	-0.01	-0.01 – 0.00	<0.01	0.00	0.00 – 0.01	0.62
Random Effects				Random Effects		
b ₀ Pond	0.08			0.63		
σ ²	0.26			0.67		
N _{Pond}	13			11		
N _{Observations}	805			674		
Marginal R ² / Conditional R ²	0.89 / 0.91			0.69 / 0.84		

6. Temporal comparisons

Table S6. Exposition of causal assumption tested by the structural equation models.		
Path	Causal assumption	Reference
Δ Canopy → Δ Temperature	Canopy influences pond site microclimate by shading radiation and altering evaporative cooling	(De Frenne et al., 2021)
Δ Canopy → Δ EP	Canopy drives microgeographic variation in embryonic development rates	(Skelly, 2004)
Δ Temperature → Δ EP	Temperature drives microgeographic variation in embryonic development rates	<i>This study</i>

Δ Egg Vol. \rightarrow Δ EP	Larger embryos represent greater provisioning which influences embryonic development rates	(Berven, 1988; Berven and Chadra, 1988; Bradford, 1990)
Δ Canopy \rightarrow Δ Egg Vol.	Microgeographic variation in canopy influences maternal condition and provisioning	(Werner and Glennemeier, 1999)
Δ Temperature \rightarrow Δ Egg Vol.	Microgeographic variation in temperature influences maternal condition and provisioning	(Berven, 1988; Rowiński et al., 2020)

References

- Anderson, M. C. (1964). Studies of the woodland light climate I. The photographic computation of light condition. *Journal of Ecology* 52, 27–41.
- Arietta, A. Z. A., Freidenburg, L. K., Urban, M. C., Rodrigues, S. B., Rubinstein, A., and Skelly, D. K. (2020). Phenological delay despite warming in wood frog *Rana sylvatica* reproductive timing: a 20-year study. *Ecography* 52, 27.
- Beckschäfer, P. (2015). Hemispherical_2.0: Batch processing hemispherical and canopy photographs with ImageJ - User manual. doi:10.13140/RG.2.1.3059.4088.
- Beckschäfer, P., Seidel, D., Kleinn, C., and Xu, J. (2013). On the exposure of hemispherical photographs in forests. *iForest* 6, 228–237.
- Berven, K. A. (1988). Factors Affecting Variation in Reproductive Traits within a Population of Wood Frogs (*Rana sylvatica*). *Copeia* 1988, 605–615.
- Berven, K. A., and Chadra, B. G. (1988). The relationship among egg size, density and food level on larval development in the wood frog (*Rana sylvatica*). *Oecologia* 75, 67–72.
- Bradford, D. F. (1990). Incubation Time and Rate of Embryonic Development in Amphibians: The Influence of Ovum Size, Temperature, and Reproductive Mode. *Physiol. Zool.* 63, 1157–1180.
- De Frenne, P., Lenoir, J., Luoto, M., Scheffers, B. R., Zellweger, F., Aalto, J., et al. (2021). Forest microclimates and climate change: Importance, drivers and future research agenda. *Glob. Chang. Biol.* doi:10.1111/gcb.15569.
- Frazer, G. W., Canham, C. D., and Lertzman, K. P. (1999). Gap Light Analyzer (GLA): Imaging software to extract canopy structure and gap light transmission indices from true-color fisheye photographs, users manual and documentation. Burnaby, British Columbia: Simon Fraser University Available at: <http://rem-main.rem.sfu.ca/downloads/Forestry/GLAV2UsersManual.pdf>.

- Glatthorn, J., and Beckschäfer, P. (2014). Standardizing the protocol for hemispherical photographs: accuracy assessment of binarization algorithms. *PLoS One* 9, e111924.
- Halverson, M. A., Skelly, D. K., Kiesecker, J. M., and Freidenburg, L. K. (2003). Forest mediated light regime linked to amphibian distribution and performance. *Oecologia* 134, 360–364.
- Jennings, S. B., Brown, N. D., and Sheil, D. (1999). Assessing forest canopies and understorey illumination: canopy closure, canopy cover and other measures. *Forestry* 72, 59–74.
- Liaw, A., and Wiener, M. (2002). Classification and Regression by randomForest. *R News* 2, 18–22. Available at: <https://CRAN.R-project.org/doc/Rnews/>.
- Promis, A. (2013). Measuring and estimating the below-canopy light environment in a forest. a review. 19, 139–146.
- Promis, A., Caldentey, J., and Cruz, G. (2012). Evaluating the usefulness of hemispherical photographs as a means to estimate photosynthetic photon flux density during a growing season in the understorey of *Nothofagus pumilio* forests. *Plant Biosystems - An International Journal Dealing with all Aspects of Plant Biology* 146, 237–243.
- Rich, P. M. (1989). *A Manual for Analysis of Hemispherical Canopy Photography*. Los Alamos National Laboratory.
- Rich, P. M. (1990). Characterizing plant canopies with hemispherical photographs. *Remote Sens. Rev.* 5, 13–29.
- Rowiński, P. K., Laurila, A., Gotthard, K., Sowersby, W., Lind, M. I., Richter-Boix, A., et al. (2020). Parental effects influence life history traits and covary with an environmental cline in common frog populations. *Oecologia* 192, 1013–1022.
- Skelly, D. K. (2004). Microgeographic countergradient variation in the wood frog, *Rana sylvatica*. *Evolution* 58, 160–165.
- Thornton, P. E., Thornton, M. M., Mayer, B. W., Wei, Y., Devarakonda, R., Vose, R. S., et al. (2016). Daymet: Daily Surface Weather Data on a 1-km Grid for North America, Version 3. doi:10.3334/ORNLDAAC/1328.
- Wagner, S. (1998). Calibration of grey values of hemispherical photographs for image analysis. *Agric. For. Meteorol.* 90, 103–117.
- Werner, E. E., and Glennemeier, K. S. (1999). Influence of Forest Canopy Cover on the Breeding Pond Distributions of Several Amphibian Species. *Copeia* 1999, 1–12.